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TRAINING THE SENSES FOR EFFECTIVE LEARNING

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Abstract

Learning is very important in human life. Learning indirectly starts form the birth itself. Infant gives responses to the light, sounds etc. As kid grownups one has to show deliberate efforts for the learning. Senses provide first hand experiences and that's why these experiences are immortal in the life of a person. Senses are the gate ways for the learning. Maria Montessori, an Italian educationist proved that kids learn easily through the senses. Direct and effective learning is possible through the senses. In all sort of learning; sense are involved. But for the effective learning senses should be given proper training. With proper training power of the senses can be increased. In the present paper how to train important senses is discussed.

Introduction-

The five senses of hearing, touch, sight, taste and smell are the key means we use to gain new knowledge. We hardly ever experience with one sense alone. Our senses work together to give us a total picture of our experiences. Maria Montessori had done various experiments for the earning of the kids. She believed that freedom & independence are very important in sensory learning. To enhance the sensory perception kids should be provided good quality toys at initial

stage. Children start responding toys with various angles. Even the principle of learning styles also can be given justice with the help of providing toys. Froebel, the founder of the kindergarten movement, Jean Itard and Edouard Seguin developed teaching materials for children. Concrete materials for the child to see, touch, hear, smell or taste plays very important role in learning. If the proper training is given to the senses learning makes effective and easy too. At the initial stage responsibility of a parent and the teacher is very important that they should help the child to discover various relations between the toys e.g. smaller, bigger, color etc. sensitivity within the children enables them to make surprisingly accurate judgments based on their perception.

Training the Five Senses to Learn -

Using many senses to receive information helps learning to be more meaningful and useful. Five senses—hearing, sight, smell, taste, and touch can be trained for the effective learning.

Sensorimotor Stage

of Swiss psychologist Jean Piaget has given stages of learning and in it sensorymotor stage is very important stage of cognitive development, it occurs during the first two years of life. This is the time when infants use their senses to explore the world around them. Cognitive development increases as children process the information their senses take in. From the beginning, infants use the senses of sight, hearing and feeling to learn and discover. During the sensorimotor stage, a child goes from being aware only of what is in her immediate environment to developing memory.

Network of Brain

Sensory experiences help to develop the brain; Brain processes different kinds of information. Cells known as sensory neurons carry information from the sensory organs to the brain. Learning occurs as the brain sorts out this information and builds new connections. Although many of the neurons in the brain aren't connected when a baby is born, the messages that neurons relay to each other create connections as learning takes place.

Cognitive Skills

In the cognitive development memory, intelligence, reasoning and problem-solving such skills are included. A child uses these abilities for the process of information which he has received from senses. Cognitive skills are learned, they can be improved. The Ask Dr. Sears suggests giving a baby toys that stimulate several senses at once to increase brain development. A toy can be simple and inexpensive, and still do the job, as long as it stimulates your child's cognitive growth.

Sight-

Sight is a major sense which is involved in learning. It can be taken for granted as most activities involve 'seeing'. From the beginning how to see & observe, and variety of learning experiences must be given to the child. For the teachers to make lessons more excellent students should be engaged with eye catching resources; black and white sheets are not motivating or stimulating and become easily boring to children. There is a fine balance between making a resource, for example a work sheet, interesting to children yet not too distracting away from the task. Use resources that incorporate colors and characters into the work itself. Actual 'looking tasks' are beneficial to children's cognitive development for example word searches, spot the difference and 'Where is ...?' as they make them pay attention to, and register small details, more. Sight tasks can be extremely memorable tools when used in an effective way- so make sure they are utilized. Matching games, to find out the word from page, optical illusion games such activities can be arranged for the purpose of developing the power of sight.

Hearing

Sound plays a crucial role for everyone in the learning. It helps children understand the world around them superior and provides another angle of understanding that viewing alone can't provide. Developing good listening habits helps children get important information, listening carefully with concentration is very important. Teacher should make arrangement to for incorporating for hearing into the classroom; it has been found that playing soft, calming music when working can help concentration so classical music CD can be played during quiet time as

background music. Additionally, there are aural tasks that offer a different type of activity which makes the everyday learning fun for children. Playing tapes that involve 'identifying and labeling' gives children the chance to develop a holistic concept; for example they may know how an animal looks like but by hearing their sound they can begin to understand more aspects of the species. Nature is just one example of where sound can aid comprehension; it is also a useful tool in PE, geography and science. In fact, it is hard to find a subject where it will not aid learning so incorporating hearing tasks into lessons will only be beneficial. Now many computer games are also available through which students can develop auditory perception in easy and effective manner. In such games audio has been played initially and child listen that audio carefully then pictures are provided child has to click the picture of the concerned thing. Giving small instructions for activity/game, sequence clapping games, memory based recitation poems can be used to improve hearing.

Taste

Everybody loves food- and it can be educational! Taste can play a big part in the syllabus. Tasting the dishes from various geographical conditions/countries is a good fore the learning. If you can associate a fact with a fun memory it helps you to retain more information. For example if you were doing yeast reactions in science actually making bread from yeast will provide a vivid image for your students to relate the scientific facts to which is reinforced further by tasting the bread. Or, irreversible reactions can use food such as boiling eggs and making jelly. So, although baking might not seem all that relevant to science by engaging multiple senses it will increase fact memory. Combination of various vegetables, fruits and tasting it, tasting foods, taste test such activities can be arranged to develop taste sense.

Smell

Smell of a particular thing is associated with the many thing of the person's life. Smell of flower, smell of a soil after first rain, makes one to remember and associate various things with that smell. The sense of smell is a very powerful tool to have at our disposal. We subconsciously associate smells with different things, for example family members, happy memories or places. This can be used in the classroom by building associations with different

smells and linking them to the lesson. If you are teaching about flowers get some particularly bitter plants for the children to inhale. The same can be applied to most subjects. Additionally, having a fresh smelling classroom makes for a successful learning environment so open the windows and invests in an air freshener to let the motivational breeze in! Don't forget about smell; this strong sense can be easily ignored and under used. Hiding the smell/scent somewhere and motivate to find out and identify, flowers and its smell, mixing the smells and fun such activities can be arrange to develop smell sense.

Touch

Children learn better if they have something in front of them that they can experience and actually touch, and even better if they made it themselves. Get your students expressing themselves using play currency, various shapes made of plastic, paint, bubble wrap, actual collected things from the environment (soft, hard,glossy) the list is endless! This is a chance to get creative with your students and let them experiment themselves through making and touching. Textures are an important tool and creativity needs to be developed at school. Lessons incorporating touch and movement will be particularly useful to kinesthetic learners and it will be fun for everyone. Paint, different woods, grass, carpet, glass, clay, water, sand, and grains such variety of items can be given to touch and feel. In the Pillow Play game familiar objects are kept inside of an empty pillowcase and child tries to guess what the objects are.

Conclusion-

Children first start learning about the world by instinctively using their five senses. So, to have a happy classroom and successful students ensure that **learning is multi-sensory** and include activities which stimulate all the senses into your lessons.

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